

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 6

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 6

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ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**KAMISHOV Sergey Viktorovich**

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**ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF
COMPULSORY HEALTH INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN**

For citation: Kamishov V. Sergey, Balenkov Y. Oleg, Niyazov G. Akmal. Analysis of trends in the development of the system of compulsory health insurance in Uzbekistan// Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 6, pp.170-177

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605472>**ANNOTATION**

The introduction of the compulsory health insurance (CHI) system in Uzbekistan is aimed at modernizing healthcare, which continues to experience difficulties with budget financing, moving from the Soviet model to a more efficient and decentralized system. The main goals of the reform are to improve access to medical services, ensure the sustainability of the healthcare system and equitable distribution of funds. The CHI project is being implemented taking into account international experience and includes regional pilot initiatives. Such problems as limited integration between levels of health care and lack of finance suggest a phased introduction of CHI, the development of public and private partnerships, as well as the expansion of medical infrastructure and improvement of personnel training.

Keywords: compulsory health insurance, healthcare system reform, public-private partnership, social insurance, sources of funding, Uzbekistan

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ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА МАЖБУРИЙ СОГ'ЛИҚ СУГ'УРТА ТИЗИМИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТЕНДЕНТЛАРИНИНГ ТАHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ўзбекистонда мажбурий tibbiy sug'urta (MAS) tizimini joriy etish sovet modelidan samaraliroq va markazlashmagan tizimga o'tish, byudjetni moliyalashtirishda qiyinchiliklar davom etayotgan sog'liqni saqlashni, sovet modelidan samaraliroq va markazlashmagan tizimga o'tish orqali modernizatsiya qilishga qaratilgan. Islohotning asosiy maqsadlari tibbiy xizmatlardan foydalanishni yaxshilash, sog'liqni saqlash tizimining barqarorligini ta'minlash va moliyani adolatli taqsimlashdan iborat. Majburiy tibbiy sug'urta loyihasi xalqaro tajribani hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirilmogda va mintaqaviy tajriba tashabbuslarini o'z ichiga oladi. Tibbiy yordam ko'rsatish darajalari o'rtasidagi integratsiyaning cheklanganligi va moliya etishmasligi kabi muammolar majburiy tibbiy sug'urtani bosqichma-bosqich joriy etish, davlat va xususiy sheriklikni rivojlantirish, shuningdek, tibbiy infratuzilmani kengaytirish va kadrlar tayyorlashni takomillashtirishni taqozo etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat-xususiy sheriklik, ijtimoiy sug'urta, majburiy tibbiy sug'urta, moliyalashtirish manbalari, O'zbekiston, sog'liqni saqlash islohoti

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АНАЛИЗ ТЕНДЕНЦИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ СИСТЕМЫ ОБЯЗАТЕЛЬНОГО МЕДИЦИНСКОГО СТРАХОВАНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение системы обязательного медицинского страхования (ОМС) в Узбекистане направлено на модернизацию здравоохранения, которое продолжает испытывать трудности с бюджетным финансированием, переходя от советской модели к более эффективной и децентрализованной системе. Главными целями реформы являются улучшение доступа к медицинским услугам, обеспечение устойчивости системы здравоохранения и справедливое распределение финансов. Проект ОМС реализуется с учетом международного опыта и включает региональные пилотные инициативы. Такие проблемы, как ограниченная интеграция между уровнями медицинской помощи и нехватка финансов, предполагают поэтапное внедрение ОМС, развитие государственного и частного партнерства, а также расширение медицинской инфраструктуры и совершенствование кадровой подготовки.

Ключевые слова: государственно-частное партнерство, источники финансирования, обязательное медицинское страхование, реформа системы здравоохранения, социальное страхование, Узбекистан

Introduction. The relevance of establishing a system of compulsory health insurance (CHI) in Uzbekistan is driven by the need to modernize the country's healthcare system, which is a critical task on the path toward sustainable development and improving the population's quality of life. The existing healthcare system, historically shaped during the Soviet era, largely relies on budgetary funding and is not always capable of effectively responding to the current and growing needs of the population. The introduction of CHI is intended to address a number of key issues, including access

to medical services, the equitable distribution of financial resources, and ensuring the financial sustainability of the sector.

Despite extensive international experience in healthcare system reforms, the transition to CHI in the context of Uzbekistan represents a unique case due to a range of specific factors. In this regard, the best approach to the challenge of creating an effective CHI system in Uzbekistan lies in an interdisciplinary approach, combining economic, sociological, managerial, and medical research. This approach will enable the development of innovative solutions to transform the country's healthcare system in the context of an emerging economy [1,2,6,8,10]

The aim of this study is to analyze trends in the development of the compulsory health insurance (CHI) system in Uzbekistan and to assess its effectiveness and potential for adaptation to the current economic and social conditions of the country. The objectives of the study include studying the current state of Uzbekistan's healthcare system and its financing, assessing international experience in CHI and its adaptation in countries with transitional economies similar to Uzbekistan, analyzing the effectiveness of implemented CHI pilot projects in Uzbekistan, identifying factors that promote or hinder their implementation, determining the financial, institutional, and structural changes needed to create a sustainable CHI system, and developing recommendations for optimizing the implementation of CHI, taking into account Uzbekistan's socio-economic characteristics and available resources.

The research methodology includes the analysis of contemporary scientific publications, the comparison of data on changes in Uzbekistan's healthcare system with international examples, and the study of the regulatory and institutional framework that defines the implementation of CHI in the country.

Healthcare financing reforms. After gaining independence, Uzbekistan initiated a series of significant reforms aimed at revitalizing the financial system. However, the country still faces considerable challenges in effectively integrating with global financial markets and creating a strong and reliable insurance sector that meets international standards. These persistent issues include the urgent need to elevate banking standards to a globally competitive level and to promote the development of non-banking financial institutions that can contribute to a more diversified and sustainable financial ecosystem [3,4,12].

Recent healthcare reforms in Uzbekistan, aimed at improving the provision and accessibility of medical services, are a key factor in the successful implementation of the CHI system. These reforms should focus on enhancing the quality of medical care, expanding access to services, and ensuring efficient resource allocation. The phased introduction of public health insurance mechanisms in medical institutions in Tashkent began on January 1, 2024, as outlined in the presidential decree on implementing the Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy in the current year. The health insurance system includes the introduction of a state-guaranteed set of free healthcare services and a list of medications by disease groups. A presidential decree issued in September set the end of 2026 as the deadline for completing the implementation of health insurance in Uzbekistan. Starting in 2024, the State Health Insurance Fund will be transferred under the Ministry of Health's structure, and by 2027, it will become an independent fund [1,2,11].

Financial Stability and Resource Allocation. A fundamental issue of the financial stability of healthcare insurance systems is a serious concern, as evidenced by the significant challenges currently faced by the pension system in Uzbekistan. This situation requires urgent attention and intervention. To ensure a reliable financial foundation, careful resource management is necessary, along with the development and implementation of sustainable financing mechanisms capable of withstanding economic fluctuations and demographic changes [12].

The transition to the CHI model, as demonstrated by Russia's experience, increases the risks associated with excessive reliance on extensive medical benefit schemes, especially in scenarios where there is an evident shortage of adequate financial resources to support such initiatives. This may lead to decreased efficiency and unrealistic expectations, which will require a realistic assessment of available resources and potential co-payment models [16]. The implementation of international financial reporting standards (IFRS) into the corporate governance system in Uzbekistan

can significantly improve transparency and accountability in financial management, which is crucial for the effective allocation and strict monitoring of funds directed towards public-private partnerships (PPP), which are vital for national development [2].

The development and improvement of financial management systems represent a crucial area of focus within the broader context of contemporary economic reforms. Specifically, the current reforms in financial management systems in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with a particular emphasis on joint-stock companies, open up significant opportunities for adapting and implementing methodologies that promote effective management of public-private partnership (PPP) funds. The main prerequisites for implementing this initiative include improving the financial management systems currently used by joint-stock companies, increasing the investment attractiveness of health insurance organizations, and promoting international integration that facilitates the adoption of globally recognized best practices [6].

The implementation of public-private partnerships (PPP) can significantly stimulate the growth of the healthcare sector by successfully attracting private investments and specialized expertise, which can enhance service quality and operational efficiency. However, there are various challenges that need to be overcome, such as significant discrepancies in strategic goals between different government agencies, which create serious obstacles to creating conditions that facilitate increased private sector involvement in these partnerships. To effectively attract private investments and ensure the active participation of private organizations within the framework of PPPs, the government must develop and promote clear incentives, as well as guarantees of the profitability of such projects [17].

Comparative Assessment with International Experience. An analysis of international healthcare financing models shows that no country has a transparent or perfectly structured model, and generally, one source of funding accounts for more than 70% of government expenditures, indicating a reliance on budgetary and insurance models. This highlights the difficulties associated with securing comprehensive healthcare funding exclusively from public resources. A comparative assessment of the CHI system in Uzbekistan can be made based on the following key criteria: financing, accessibility and quality of healthcare services, private sector involvement, and social guarantees for citizens. When comparing Uzbekistan's CHI system with similar systems in other countries, both common features and unique characteristics can be identified [2,10].

In most countries with a developed CHI system, there are three main sources of funding for this fund:

Budget contributions – funds allocated by the government to ensure the functioning of the healthcare insurance system and cover the costs of medical services for citizens.

Entrepreneur contributions – employer contributions, where employers are required to make payments for the health insurance of their employees.

Personal contributions from citizens – contributions made by citizens themselves, who participate in the CHI system and pay part of the costs for medical services.

In the CHI system of Uzbekistan, funding is formed through the contributions of insurers, including government funds and employer contributions. A phased approach is being implemented for the creation of the CHI fund in Uzbekistan, starting with individual regions, which allows for adjustments to policies based on regional characteristics and needs. In countries with a developed CHI system (such as Germany or Japan), the health insurance fund is formed from three sources: the state budget, employer funds, and personal contributions from citizens. This allows for the distribution of financial burden and increases the system's stability. In Uzbekistan, the financing system is still in the process of formation, and its further development may include the involvement of additional sources, such as personal contributions from citizens [10,14].

In Uzbekistan, the phased implementation of CHI is aimed at improving access to essential medical services, such as emergency care, consultations, vaccination, and testing, which are funded by the government. The CHI fund directs funds to institutions offering quality services, while also developing quality control, staff training, and infrastructure modernization [1]. Uzbekistan intends to gradually eliminate the differences between public and private clinics to ensure equal quality of

healthcare services. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) play an important role in facilitating the attraction of private investments and expertise. In countries with a developed CHI system, the private sector is often actively involved in providing healthcare services, which expands opportunities for citizens and improves the competitive environment. For example, in the Netherlands and Switzerland, health insurance companies operate independently, allowing patients to choose from a wide range of private and public providers [6].

The healthcare financing reforms implemented in Kyrgyzstan could serve as a good model for Uzbekistan. By creating a unified national pool and applying outcome-based payment methods, Kyrgyzstan skillfully combined various sources of healthcare financing into a single system. This strategy emphasizes the importance of pooling resources and reconfiguring financial mechanisms to promote universal population coverage [13]. In Azerbaijan, the creation of PPPs as a pilot initiative highlighted the crucial role of developing insurance markets and expanding insurance services to improve the level of healthcare provision. The emergence of public-private partnerships in Azerbaijan as a pilot project provides important insights. The initiative emphasized the need for resource allocation and the effectiveness of contributions from the state and market participants to the healthcare sector [9,10].

Ensuring universal access to healthcare services in various Asian countries, including Indonesia, underscores the necessity of eliminating material, technical, and administrative barriers. These challenges include ensuring equal access to services, maintaining quality, and achieving financial sustainability [15]. Countries like China and Thailand have faced significant difficulties in extending insurance coverage to the informal sector while simultaneously ensuring protection against financial risks. This experience highlights the need for Uzbekistan to create an CHI system to address similar issues, including the excessive use of resources and equal access [18].

Prospects for the Development of the CHI System in Uzbekistan. To tackle these multifaceted problems, Uzbekistan should wisely implement a methodological strategy for healthcare financing reform, drawing on the effective methodologies applied by other countries. This includes creating a final benefits package, strengthening financial oversight, and establishing efficient service delivery mechanisms. Key measures include strengthening the link between primary and secondary healthcare and eliminating regional disparities in healthcare financing. This requires strategic investments in healthcare infrastructure and workforce development, especially in underserved rural areas [1].

The CHI system in Uzbekistan is in the process of gradual implementation, expanding the benefits package and financial autonomy of healthcare institutions. Unlike developed systems, it adapts to local conditions and requires new financing mechanisms, standardization of per capita budgets, and a contractual system to ensure free healthcare services. CHI supports economic stability by protecting businesses and citizens. The introduction of social insurance and adaptation to international standards creates opportunities to improve access to healthcare and financial protection, but requires consideration of economic conditions and population needs [5,7,10].

The pilot project for the introduction of state medical insurance (SMI) in Uzbekistan was launched in the Syrdarya region in July 2021 with the aim of improving the provision and access to medical services. The project is being implemented based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) and covers two key areas of reform: the financing system and the medical care system. This involves transitioning from financing infrastructure (such as hospital beds and utilities) to paying for the actual medical services provided to patients. This means that funds are now directed to pay for the medical services needed by specific individuals. The second area is changing clinical practice with a focus on medical service outcomes rather than the treatment process, as well as increasing the accessibility of these services to the population. The pilot project has shown good results in these areas [2,8].

As part of the project, a free package of medical services financed from the state budget through the State Medical Insurance Fund (SMIF) was created. The Fund purchases services from medical institutions. The SMIF acts as an intermediary, directing funds directly to the accounts of institutions, ensuring their financial independence. Thanks to improved management skills,

healthcare institutions will gain more autonomy, which will ultimately ensure equal access to quality services in both public and private clinics. This guaranteed free package includes:

- Emergency ambulance services and hospitalization in urgent cases;
- Primary healthcare visits and consultations with specialized doctors;
- Laboratory tests and diagnostic examinations as prescribed by the family doctor;
- Preventive check-ups and vaccinations according to the National Immunization Calendar;
- Outpatient treatment, medical rehabilitation, and palliative care;
- Prescription medications from the list approved by the Ministry of Health.

A reimbursement system is also being implemented, allowing patients to receive medications free of charge through electronic prescriptions issued by their family doctor. The results of the pilot project in the Syrdarya region will serve as the basis for further expanding access to guaranteed and quality healthcare in other regions of Uzbekistan, using the new healthcare organization model. To expand access to quality medical services, the phased implementation of the CHI system in the Navoi region began on January 1, 2023. The project was then extended to the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the city of Tashkent on October 1, 2023. On January 1, 2024, the implementation of CHI continued in the Samarkand, Surkhandarya, and Fergana regions. These measures are aimed at creating more accessible and quality healthcare for citizens, improving healthcare financing, and enhancing the effectiveness of medical service delivery [8].

Our recommendations for optimizing the implementation of the CHI system in Uzbekistan, considering socio-economic features and available resources, include the following key directions:

1. Financial Sustainability and Diversification of Funding Sources

- Gradual Introduction of Contributions: Given the economic situation of citizens and employers in Uzbekistan, it may not be feasible to immediately implement high-level mandatory contributions. It is recommended to start with minimal contributions, which can be gradually increased.
- Use of a Multi-Level Funding System: The optimal solution would be a combination of the state budget, employer contributions, and a gradually increasing contribution from citizens. This will reduce the burden on any one side and ensure the system's stability.
- State Subsidies for Vulnerable Groups: Subsidies should be provided for low-income groups to ensure equitable access to healthcare services and protect the most vulnerable citizens.

2. Improving Infrastructure and Human Resources

- Investing in Healthcare Infrastructure: For the effective implementation of CHI, healthcare facilities, particularly in rural areas, need to be developed. Investments should focus on modernizing equipment, improving hospital conditions, and increasing access to primary healthcare.
- Improving Medical Personnel Qualifications: Retraining programs for doctors and medical staff, along with training courses in CHI management, will ensure high-quality services and efficient resource distribution.

3. Pilot Projects and Phased Implementation

- Continued Implementation of Pilot Projects: Based on the experience of pilot projects in the Syrdarya and Navoi regions, it is recommended to expand the practice of testing CHI in new regions, identifying local features, and adjusting the program as it scales.
- Phased Introduction of CHI in Other Regions: Regions should be connected to the CHI system gradually, taking into account their economic development level and available resources, ensuring smoother implementation and adaptation to the system.

4. Measures to Increase Accessibility of Medical Services

- Reducing Barriers for the Informal Sector: Since a significant portion of the population works in the informal sector, it is important to develop special mechanisms to include these citizens in the CHI system, such as through subsidized contributions or flexible participation conditions.
- Developing Telemedicine and Mobile Clinics: For remote and rural areas where healthcare facilities are scarce, telemedicine services and mobile clinics should be more widely implemented to compensate for the lack of medical services.

5. Strengthening Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)

- **Creating Incentives for Private Investments:** PPP can help increase healthcare funding and introduce innovations that improve the quality of services. This requires offering tax incentives and profitability guarantees for private partners.

- **Transparency and Accountability:** A crucial step is the implementation of international standards for financial reporting and management practices in the PPP system, which will build investor trust and ensure transparency in the use of funds.

6. **Monitoring and System Adaptation Based on International Experience**

- **Regular Evaluation and Monitoring of Effectiveness:** Monitoring structures should be established to evaluate the results of reforms and make timely adjustments, taking into account international experience and internal needs.

- **Adapting Best Practices:** The experience of countries that have successfully implemented CHI systems can help Uzbekistan optimize its funding and resource management policies.

Conclusion. The transition to the Compulsory Health Insurance (CHI) system in Uzbekistan presents both challenges and opportunities for improving healthcare and financing. The analysis highlights the need for this system to enhance the quality and accessibility of medical services in the context of a transitional economy. The existing healthcare model, a relic of the Soviet era, inadequately meets modern needs due to centralized financing problems and resource distribution issues. Therefore, the shift to CHI represents a strategic initiative aimed at creating a more adaptable, transparent, and financially sound healthcare system that ensures equal access for all demographic groups.

Pilot initiatives in various regions show that a patient-centered approach can improve the quality of healthcare and the financial independence of medical institutions. These initiatives also include free service packages that increase the accessibility of essential medical services, which is critical for state-guaranteed healthcare coverage. The experience of other countries with similar socio-economic contexts can aid in the development of an effective national CHI model that takes into account Uzbekistan's unique conditions. Creating a basic benefits package is essential to ensure universal coverage, guaranteeing access to quality medical services. The focus on modernizing healthcare infrastructure will improve the quality of care and optimize resource utilization within the CHI system.

Our recommendations aim to develop a sustainable and economically viable CHI system that will enhance the quality and accessibility of healthcare services for Uzbekistan's citizens while providing a stable financial model for the long-term development of healthcare. By addressing these challenges and leveraging global experience, Uzbekistan can create a reliable CHI system that meets the population's healthcare needs.

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ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 6

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